

A novel generative research dataset on preprints' role within the Covid-19 pandemic

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Introduction

Studies on researchers' publication behaviour as well as on outer-academic stakeholders' reception of research findings during the Covid-19 pandemic indicate that this unprecedented global crisis profoundly affected the system of science communication (Watson, 2022). An example for such an effect is the observed rise of preprints as a format to quickly disseminate novel insights. Ten months into the pandemic, about 25% of all published Covid-19-related research articles were preprints (Fraser et al., 2021). At the same time, the Covid-19 crisis involved a surge of reporting on scientific preprints within news media (Flecker et al., 2022). Preprints' usually non-peer-reviewed and sometimes preliminary nature can make their assessment challenging, particularly for readers from outside of the respective subject field. Moreover, due to their limited coverage within prominent bibliographic databases, preprints have received less attention within scientometric studies than formal publication formats so far.

The paramount purpose of this research project is to develop a comprehensive, enriched dataset of Covid-19-related preprints, assisting three primary user groups in navigating the bulk of preprinted research on Covid-19: journalists, health experts, and scientometricians. The dataset shall provide informative publication-level metadata that enable detailed classifications of individual preprints, aid stakeholders such as journalists in relevance assessments, and prepare future scientometric analyses of the preprint-based communication of research within the pandemic. Furthermore, by presenting our results in the innovative form of a generative dataset, we hope to help induce the scientometric community to reflect and discuss in which formats to best share and work with (partly) open data in the future.

This poster presents an overview over the dataset's creation, contents, structure, and an outlook towards potential complements in the future.

Methods for the Dataset's Creation

In this project's initial phase, potential sources for the intended dataset were gathered and assessed in terms of comprehensiveness and accessibility. The decision was made for *Dimensions* as the dataset's core source, due to its straightforward and for research purposes free accessibility, as well as its comparatively rich amount of preprint-related data.

To be able to comply with *Dimensions*' licensing terms, we follow the approach of a generative dataset. Thus, the dataset does not get published as a downloadable dump, but in the form of computational notebooks that interested users can download and run to construct their own instances of the dataset using the *Dimensions Analytics API*ⁱ. All necessary files are freely available onlineⁱⁱ.

To identify Covid-19-related preprints, we rely on the search string recommended by *Dimensions* for this purposeⁱⁱⁱ. The respective API query across titles and abstracts leads to a total of 33,402 articles with *type=preprint* from publication year 2020, which is the basis for the exemplary analyses on the poster.

Preliminary concepts for the dataset were also discussed in an online workshop with representatives of the mentioned primary user groups. The goals were to assess the value of the prototypical data enrichments by collecting feedback, as well as to gather users' ideas regarding their potential use cases for and promising additions to the dataset.

Dataset Structure and Application Examples

The generative dataset's contents are structured within five layers (see Figure 1 for an overview).

The pipeline for the dataset's generation starts with the metadata layer, which contains basic publication information obtained from *Dimensions' Analytics API* via the initial query for Covid-19-related preprints. Such publication information includes features like the article's DOI, title, abstract, publication date, citation count, Altmetric Attention Score, its publishing journal's SCImago Journal Rank and SNIP (if applicable), full text link, link to a resulting publication (if applicable), its authors and their affiliations, as well as various subject categorizations offered by *Dimensions* (e.g., *HRA*

Heal Research Areas or BRA Broad Research Areas). These metadata are also the basis for the generation of the dataset's remaining four layers.

Figure 1. Schematic overview over the generative dataset's five layers.

The second layer consists of co-author-networks of the preprints' authors. Unification of authors is enriched through matching with disambiguated author IDs from *OpenAlex*^{iv}.

The dataset's third layer includes the preprints' full texts. For this, PDF files linked within Dimensions' records are downloaded and converted to the standardized, structured, and machine-readable format XML/TEI. This enables convenient further steps of processing, e.g., to extract references and their contexts within the preprints.

The fourth layer of the dataset consists of document embeddings, i.e., high-dimensional and dense representations of the documents as vectors, based on the preprints' titles and abstracts.

The fifth layer draws data from Semantic Scholar to provide contexts and intents of citations within the preprints' full texts.

The dataset's five layers provide the means to tackle a highly diverse range of research questions. The metadata included in the dataset's first layer already provides a basis to address a multitude of questions of interest, e.g., in which journals Covid-19-related preprints ultimately get published, which properties particularly impactful preprints share, etc.. Author networks provided by layer 2 could be used to cluster research groups, model patterns of cooperation, or analyze if and how reputation can be handed down across such networks. To journalists, these networks might provide assistance in estimating specific authors' prominence or relevance. The full text data from layer 3 enables a multitude of applications in natural language processing. Layer 4's document embeddings provide a basis to for instance analyze the prevalence and development of certain subtopics within Covid-19-related research publications over time, while the citation intents in layer 5 could help to distinguish articles' argumentative approaches.

Conclusions

We present an approach that shall provide journalists, scientometricians, health professionals, and other stakeholder groups with convenient access to a comprehensive, enriched dataset of Covid-19-related preprints. Our generative comes with certain advantages as well as disadvantages. On the one hand, organizing the dataset within computational notebooks allows the easy inclusion of effective demos of how to handle the dataset as well as of exemplary, basic analyses. Moreover, large parts of the provided notebooks function as a generic pipeline for processing publication data. Our approach therefore also serves as an example for how (relatively) open data can be curated further with comparative ease in order to fulfil more specific user needs. The two major drawbacks of such a generative dataset based on Dimensions data are that interested users (1) need to have (or apply for) their own Dimensions API key, and (2) are required to bring a basic level of programming expertise in order to run the notebooks.

Numerous future additions to the dataset are conceivable. Further links to additional open data sources could be added, such as ORCID IDs of researchers represented in the dataset. Also, the dataset's layers 2 to 5 could be refined, for instance by leveraging layer 3's full text data to classify articles' argumentative approaches, or by utilizing layer 4's document embeddings to arrive at granular topic models for Covid-19-related preprints.

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References

- Fleerackers, A., Riedlinger, M., Moorhead, L., Ahmed, R., & Alperin, J. P. (2022). Communicating Scientific Uncertainty in an Age of COVID-19: An Investigation into the Use of Preprints by Digital Media Outlets. *Health Communication*, 37(6), 726–738. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10410236.2020.1864892>
- Fraser, N., Brierley, L., Dey, G., Polka, J. K., Pálffy, M., Nanni, F., & Coates, J. A. (2021). The evolving role of preprints in the dissemination of COVID-19 research and their impact on the science communication landscape. *PLOS Biology*, 19(4), e3000959. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pbio.3000959>
- Watson, C. (2022). Rise of the preprint: How rapid data sharing during COVID-19 has changed science forever. *Nature Medicine*, 28(1), Art. 1. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41591-021-01654-6>

ⁱ <https://www.dimensions.ai/dimensions-apis/>

ⁱⁱ <https://media.sciencemediacenter.de/share/mewikoco-ds/>

ⁱⁱⁱ See also <https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.11961063.v42>.

^{iv} <https://openalex.org/>